

TESTING OF THE MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RECYCLED GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER FOR THE USE IN LOAD-BEARING STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

As the use of Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) in civil engineering in load-bearing structures is increasing there is a larger need for uniform testing procedures for some basic material characteristics. So far American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) provides some basic rules for testing of different material characteristics. Also, with the increase of material use, the need to recycle emerges and the use of the Recycled Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (RGFRP) is the next logical step. This paper analyses the basic characteristics of such recycled material and also questions some simple applications of this material in civil engineering. The aim is also to establish whether the current standards can be applied to the recycled material and whether is it necessary to make some adjustments to the testing procedures. Also, the aim is to propose some basic instructions when choosing a material or some of its components for a load-bearing structure in civil engineering with special notice to the characteristics that are desired from a material. Testing of samples for some basic characteristics like yield point, strength, modulus of elasticity and shear modulus under simple actions such as compression, tension, shear and bending in both materials (GFRP and RGFRP) are conducted and appropriate diagrams are proposed in order to fully describe the tested materials so that they can be used in common engineering calculations and design for load-bearing structures. As the load-bearing structures are very different in size and application this paper will also try to answer what is the influence of model for the material characteristics testing to real construction size ratio.

1 INTRODUCTION

New and modern load-bearing structures in civil engineering every day face a need to improve its characteristics. The emphasis is made on overall strength, strength over weight ratio, homogenous structure of the material and thus accurate prediction, calculation and design. But beside these characteristics, easy production, durability and sustainability are increasingly important factors when choosing a material for load-bearing structures. Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) is a material that has the capability to meet all the demands that modern load-bearing structures ask and as its use is increasing, in general and in civil engineering, it is becoming a more cost efficient choice. With the increase use of this material a need to investigate its full life cycle emerges. Composites like GFRP consist of a matrix and glass fibres. The fibres can be laid in different manners but always oriented

into direction of the most efficient transfer of the load through the construction. The matrix has the role to bond the fibres and transfer the load between them. It also forms the final appearance of the material and preserves it from the outside influences such as water, salt and similar different hostile environments.

In order to define a certain material and afterwards be able to design a construction from it one needs to know the following characteristics: tensile strength, compressive strength, shear strength and bending strength. These characteristics are tested on samples defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) [1].

2 THE TESTED MATERIALS

For the “original” (Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer – GFRP) material a commonly used [2] combination of polyurethane resin matrix (2/3 of the mass) and glass fibre mat (1/3 of the mass) was chosen. It was produced using a 450 g/m² glass fibre mat in two layers that have the same amount of fibres in two perpendicular directions. This resulted in sample thickness of roughly 4-5 mm.

The samples have been made from the recycled material (Recycled Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer – RGFRP) consisting of 50 % of milled waste glass fibre reinforced polymer and 50 % of polyurethane resin. The waste GFRP is milled with blades of 4 mm in diameter which produce particles with the smallest diameter of approximately 2 mm. For the fibres only one layer of 450 g/m² mat is used for the RGFRP. The recycled material is also produced in panels with the thickness of roughly 4-5 mm. It has approximately 15 % higher mass per volume and roughly 30-35 % lower production cost then the GFRP.

2.1 Tensile strength

Both materials were tested on tension. Although there are a large number of proposed samples to be used for tensile specimens only one was chosen [3]. The dimensions of the samples are shown in Figure 1 and in Table 1.

Figure 1: Dimensions of the tensile samples [mm].

Sample	b [mm]	t [mm]
1	14,3	4,3
2	14,7	4,6
3	15,6	5,0
4	15,4	4,5
5	16,4	3,7
6	15,7	4,2

Table 1: Samples dimensions for the tensile testing (Samples 1-3 GFRP, Samples 4-6 RGFRP).

Both materials were tested on three samples. The results for the GFRP are shown in Figure 2 and for the RGFRP in Figure 3. On both diagrams at the approximately 10 % of the ultimate tensile force a slight jump of the strain can be seen. This phenomenon is occurring due to settling of the jaws with which the specimens were held (Figure 4). The GFRP exhibits a slight deviation of the curve which is an indicator that the deformation is both elastic and plastic. This was also confirmed with cracking

sounds during the testing procedure. The RGFRP samples exhibit slightly less bent Stress/Strain curve which can be attributed to less plastic deformation until approximately 85 % of the ultimate load. From that to the breaking point the samples exhibit small cracks which can be seen on the diagram as small decreases of stress with continuous increase of strain. This phenomenon can be attributed to the structure of the recycled material which is mostly consisted of the matrix made from the recycled material. In general, the recycled material shows just slightly smaller ultimate tensile strength and the plastic deformation is concentrated in the area with the force of more than 85 % of the breaking value. Also the overall strain of the RGFRP is greater than the one of the GFRP which is a consequence of the more rigid or less elastic matrix. The reason to this later plastic behaviour is the use of only one mate in production of the RGFRP and thus the plastic deformations are a direct consequence of the matrix deformation rather than the fibres.

Tensile stress and strain is calculated with the next equations:

$$\sigma_t = F / A = F / (b \cdot t) \text{ [N/mm}^2\text{]} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = \Delta l / l \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Stress/Strain of the GFRP (samples 1-3) samples in tension.

Figure 3: Stress/Strain of the RGFRP (samples 4-6) samples in tension.

Figure 4: Tensile testing samples.

2.2 Compressive strength

Testing compressive strength always deals with some stability problems of the samples and there are several proposed procedures for testing the compression strength [4]. In order to avoid this problems the compression testing was conducted on samples of small dimensions (Figure 5) that were inserted in a metal tube which would not allow any buckling or similar instability that would influence the overall compressive strength. The dimensions of the samples are shown in Table 2.

Figure 5: Compression testing samples [mm].

Sample	b [mm]	t [mm]
1	9,0	4,5
2	8,7	4,2
3	9,0	4,0
4	9,0	4,5
5	8,5	4,4
6	8,5	4,3

Table 2: Samples dimensions for the compression testing (Samples 1-3 GFRP, Samples 4-6 RGFRP).

The testing was conducted on three samples for each material (GFRP and RGFRP) as shown in Figure 6. On both materials one sample displayed non characteristic behaviour/results and was considered to be a non valid test (Sample 1 and Sample 5, Figure 6). This occurred because of the uneven surface at the force application point at the sample and load concentration caused local failure of the sample before the full force could be applied. Although special attention was given to the preparation of the samples because of their small size the problem was not avoided on the mentioned two samples.

As seen in Figure 7 the GFRP exhibits approximately 8-10 % higher values of peak forces with the similar relative deformation. This behaviour can be attributed to the use of less resin/matrix in total

with RGFRP rather than with the GFRP. Compression testing setting and all samples (Samples 1-3 GFRP, Samples 4-6 RGFRP) are shown in Figure 8.

Compressive stress and strain is calculated with the next equation:

$$\sigma_c = F / A = F / (b \cdot t) \text{ [N/mm}^2\text{]} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Stress/Strain of the compression testing (Samples 1-6).

Figure 7: Stress/Strain of the compression testing (Samples 2, 3 – GFRP and 4, 6 – RGFRP).

Figure 8: Compression testing setting and samples.

2.3 Shear testing

Shear testing was conducted also on three samples of each material (GFRP and RFRP) as shown in Figure 9. The sample dimensions and shape was taken from [1] and are shown in Table 3 and Figure 10 [5]. Both materials exhibit similar capabilities for shear strength.

Figure 9: Shear testing setting and samples.

Sample	b [mm]	h [mm]	A [mm ²]	F [kN]	f_v [N/mm ²]
1	12,1	3,8	46,0	1,93	41,96
2	11,1	3,6	40,0	1,85	46,25
3	10,5	3,7	38,9	1,48	38,05
4	11,5	4,9	56,4	2,43	43,09
5	10,0	4,7	47,0	1,84	39,15
6	11,5	4,5	51,8	1,92	37,07

Table 3: Samples dimensions for the shear testing (Samples 1-3 GFRP, Samples 4-6 RFRP).

Figure 10: Shear testing samples dimensions [mm].

2.4 Bending testing

Samples tested on bending were stripes dimensions as shown in Figure 11 and the testing settings were as shown in Figure 12 as proposed in [6].

Figure 11: Bending testing samples dimensions [mm].

Figure 12: Bending testing setting and samples.

Samples were tested with a three point bending test. Both materials were tested on three samples (GFRP – Samples 1-3 and RGFPR – Samples 4-6). On the diagrams that describe the behaviour of bending samples Force/Deformation ratio is shown. Because of the linearity of the relation nothing would be gained by altering the diagrams into some other units (M, f_m or similar). All six samples have a similar deformation upon failure (approximately 25 mm).

Sample	b [mm]	t [mm]
1	39,2	3,9
2	38,9	4,0
3	38,3	3,8
4	39,6	4,3
5	39,2	4,1
6	38,9	4,2

Table 4: Samples dimensions for the bending testing (Samples 1-3 GFRP, Samples 4-6 RGFPR).

GFRP samples show a mildly curved trend of the Force/Deformation curve which is a characteristic behaviour of an elastoplastic material. RGFPR performs as an elastic material until

approximately 85% of the ultimate capacity. After that point the force does not increase with the increase of deformation. This continues until the increase of deformation of approximately 15 % after which the increase of force continues. This is a false continuing of the elastic behaviour that ends very quickly with a brittle failure.

Bending stress can be calculated with the next equation:

$$\sigma_m = M / W = (F \cdot L) / (4 \cdot W) [N/mm^2] \quad (4)$$

Figure 13: Force/Deformation diagram for the bending testing (GFRP – Samples 1-3).

Figure 14: Force/Deformation diagram for the bending testing (RGFRP – Samples 4-6).

3 PROPOSED DIAGRAMS AND CALCULATED MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 Compressive strength

Proposed diagram for compressive strength of both materials is shown in Figure 15. The limit strain for elastic compression is proposed to be set at $\epsilon = 0,022$. According to the proposed, the module of elasticity for compression would be $E = 4500 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (GFRP) and $E = 3700 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (RGFRP). With the proposed limits the compressive yield strength would be $f_c = 100 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (GFRP) and $f_c = 80 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (RGFRP).

Figure 15: Proposed Stress/Strain diagram for the compression testing.

3.2 Tension strength

Proposed diagram for tension strength of both materials is shown in Figure 16. The limit strain for elastic tension is proposed to be set at $\epsilon = 0,010$ (GFRP) and at $\epsilon = 0,008$ (RGFRP). According to the proposed, the module of elasticity for tension could be equal to both materials $E = 3900\text{-}4000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (GFRP and RGFRP). With the proposed limits the tension yield strength would be $f_t = 40 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (GFRP) and $f_t = 32 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (RGFRP).

Figure 16: Proposed Stress/Strain diagram for the tension test.

4 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The investigated material characteristics of both materials, Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) and Recycled Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (RGFRP), can be accurately determined by the existing methods. The difference in the investigated characteristics between the materials is not excessive and the recycled material is a valid choice for load-bearing structures. In general the recycled material in its tested form behaves more brittle than the original which is a negative feature but not in a manner that should exclude its use. In the specific situations the RGFRP can even be a better choice than the original GFRP [7].

4.1 Tension

The tensile capacity is roughly similar but the restraint is that the RGFRP exhibits concentrated plastic deformation above a certain load (over 85 % of the ultimate load). This characteristic limits the yield strength to a lower value than the GFRP's. Also the strain and/or deformation is slightly higher which is not a decisive feature and is related to the smaller usage of new fibres. The future research should be oriented on recycled materials with different percentage of new fibres in order to resolve this issue. One more way to improve this problem is different, mostly bigger, grinding equipment that would result in bigger particles of the recycled material. This idea produces more particles that are longer and can be used in the recycled material as new smaller fibres. Commonly, the grinding machines cannot grind the fibres into small particles and they remain as some sort of fibres. These new/old fibres take a new/old role of reinforcement/fibres.

4.2 Compression

Compressive capacity is slightly lower concerning ultimate value but has similar strain values for both materials. This is a consequence of a lesser use of new resin in production of the recycled material. This situation causes a smaller ability to bear larger compressive forces as the matrix cannot bond all of the recycled and new fibre material. This produces smaller compressive load capacity at

the same deformation level. The use of more resin would improve the overall compressive strength but it should be tested on various new samples with different resin share. The problem of small samples and unfavourable load concentration should be solved by coupling of several samples in a similar tube in order to avoid and reduce the influence of this issue.

4.3 Shear

Shear strength showed to be similar for both materials and both materials exhibited large deviations between specimens. The reason for this is the problem of small samples area that is subjected to local imperfections of both materials. This implies that the testing should be done on greater samples and more specimens. Also, shear capacity differs when considering the fibre direction in comparison to the load direction and the conducted testing considers only one orientation.

4.4 Bending

Bending capacity of GFRP displays typical elastoplastic behaviour as the RGFRP displays typical linear/elastic behaviour. Beside that RGFRP shows a specific area on the diagram near the ultimate capacity where the deformation increases at the same level of the applied force. After this a false elastic behaviour continues and quickly ends with a brittle failure. This phenomenon is a consequence of the failure of the original fibre mat and the post and false elastic behaviour is a consequence of the recycled mat bearing capacity. RGFRP exhibits more positive behaviour than GFRP in the elastic area which makes it a better option. The combination of "major" (original) fibres with "minor" (recycled) fibres seems to be a good option what can be a base for choosing and/or changing desirable RGFRP material characteristics. A difference that should not be neglected is that the GFRP samples have only one side treated with the finishing layer as the RGFRP has both sides treated.

5 CONCLUSION

Applications of the RGFRP definitely can be found in all the areas where the GFRP is already in use. Its advantage is, beside the preferable life cycle, a more compact structure that can be more resistant to some environments than the original GFRP. Also, the existence of "major" and "minor" fibres is a better solution in which a wider spectrum of stresses is covered. That information is also relevant when choosing a material for a specific purpose or construction and can be significantly altered by applying a different method of recycling [8]. The influence of size of the specimens has a significant role and a revision should be made in that sense. A proposition is to use the maximal dimensions for the specimens to be tested in order to avoid the problems mentioned in this paper. A relation between models and specimens is another issue and although it is not excluded no relation could be made from this research.

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